

Savings and Investment Pattern of Ug & Pg Teaching Faculty – A Study With Reference To Mangalore City

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Abstract:

Mangalore city is one of the famous educational centres in India. Quality of education has attracted students from all over the country and even from abroad. It is assumed by many people that Mangalorean's are smart in terms of intelligence and studies. Teachers are the pillars of society and the quality of education depends on their knowledge and skills. The interest of the teachers towards the saving and investment will have a great impact on the quality of education. In this paper, analysis is made to examine the saving and investment pattern among the UG and PG teachers in Mangalore city. The data is collected from 100 respondents with the help of a structured questionnaire based on convenience sampling. The objective of the study was to study the savings and investment pattern of UG & PG teachers, to identify the savings and investment options they use currently and analyse the factors they consider while investing and investment awareness among the UG and PG teachers. The study also focuses on the other aspects like problems faced by the teachers while investing and saving.

Keywords: Saving and Investment Pattern, Teacher's Income

Introduction:

Savings refers to the money one has saved, especially through a bank or official scheme for a given period. Savings means different things to different people. To some, it means putting money in the bank⁽⁷⁾ To others, it means buying stocks or contributing to a pension plan, medical plan, and specific purpose plan but to economists, saving means only one thing that is consuming less out of a given amount of resources in the present to consume more in the future.⁽¹¹⁾

Investment is usually the result of forgoing consumption. On the other hand, Investment refers to the action or process of investing money for profit. It is nothing but using some amount of money to help to make it grow by buying assets that might increase in value over some time. It refers to the usage of funds intending to gain a return.

Savings and Investment in India:

In the year 1683 the first bank in India 'The Madras Bank' was established, followed by the Bank of Bombay, founded in 1720, which is then followed by the Bank of Hindustan, founded in 1770. Until the decade of the '90s, most middle-class Indians were paying little attention to managing personal finance during their working life span, and only at the time of retirement, they would consult their good wishers or advisors about some deposit schemes with banks or post offices or companies which would ensure the regular monthly or quarterly returns. A very small percentage of the rich and daring or adventurous Indians would experiment in stock markets or UTI schemes. But post-1991, change came suddenly to finance and this column maps some of those changes as India celebrates 70 years of political and 26 years of economic freedom.⁽²⁶⁾ The importance of correct advice at the right time is appreciated and an average Indian is trying his or her best to develop personal finance.

Status of teachers in India:

Teaching is one of the most popular professions across the globe.⁽⁹⁾ Teachers are an important force in our society, as they are guarantors of the education of future generations, especially in developing countries like India. The competency of the teacher is a major determinant of the quality of education. A teacher's professional advancement is decided by many factors. One of the main factors which strongly influence the efficiency of the teacher is his/her quality of life. The quality of one's life is closely related to the standard of living maintained by that person. The presence or absence of certain material items, such as homes, cars, and jewellery is commonly associated with a standard of life. The ability to spend money for entertainment, health, education, variety in life, art, music, and travel also contribute to the standard of life. Large expensive or fancy items are viewed as evidence of a high standard of living (Laurence J Gitman, 1981). Thus management of personal finance i.e. income, consumption, saving, and investment have a great impact on the standard of living.

So the attitude of teachers towards consumption, savings, and investment would reflect their economic behaviour, which would influence their quality of life and in turn influence their profession and the education system. The starting point in searching for the perfect investment plan would be to examine the investor's needs. If all the needs of investment are met by the investment plan, then that particular investment can be termed the right choice.

Literature Review:

Nallakannu and Selvaraj (2018): titled "Savings and Investment Pattern of College Teachers" the study explains that Investors are sensitive about the safety of their investments. They need safety and security for their investments. It is evident from the study that most teachers consider safety for selecting

the mode of saving. Bank deposits are given first preference followed by Insurance.

Manasi Kulkarni (Killedar) (2016): et.al titled "Investment Patterns of College Teachers with respect to Navi-Mumbai city" have studied that money plays a major role in an individual's life. The researcher also came to know how much the teaching community is aware of investment knowledge. Their most preferred avenues are all traditional investments like bank deposits, government securities, bullions (gold, silver), and real estate.

Dr. Ananthapadhnabha Achar (2012): titled "Savings and Investment behaviour of Teachers - An Empirical study" analyzed that individual characteristics of teachers such as age, gender, marital status, and lifestyle to determine the savings and investment behaviour of the teaching community in the study region. In a more or less similar manner, their family characteristics such as monthly family income, stage of the family life cycle, and upbringing status emerged as determinants of their savings and investment behaviour.

Bhardwaj Rajesh, RahejaRekh, and Priyanka (2011): titled "Analysis of Income and Savings Pattern of Government and Private Senior Secondary School Teachers", Most of the government & Private teachers use bank deposits and life insurance to invest their money. In contrast to private teachers, government school teachers got more benefits. The main goal of government teachers' savings is emergency and security, while children's education for a private teacher.

Vyshak P. K., Vishnu P. K., and Sindhu Sasi (2019): studied "Savings and Investment Behaviour of College Teachers and Higher Secondary School Teachers: A Comparative Analysis". The research concluded that the Investment pattern of college and higher secondary school teachers is consistent with the traditional pattern of investment they have been using for years. Bank deposit is the most preferred investment avenue for almost all respondents.

Yasodha and Ravindran (2015): the paper "Savings and Investment Pattern of Teachers Working in Arts and Science Colleges in Coimbatore District" explains that Investors are sensitive about the safety of their investments made. They need safety and security for their investments. The current trend had not affected investment. College teachers invest their money in a safer environment and need regular income from their investment made with lower risk.

Jeyakumari and soundaravalli (2015): in their study title "A study on saving and investment pattern of college teachers with reference to Thanjavur City Corporation", which is conducted by taking a limited number of sample sizes as stated

earlier. There might be a chance that the perceptions of the different respondents are varied due to diversity in social life, living patterns, Income level, and the like. All the age groups give more importance to investing in Insurance, bank deposits, and post offices rather than any other investment avenues.

Hypothesis:

H₁: There is a relationship between Income level and the savings of the teachers.

H₂: Teachers are fully aware of the Investment avenues.

H₃: Individual/Demographic characteristics will determine the decisions to save and invest.

Need for the study:

The determinants of savings in an urban environment need not be relevant in a rural environment. Considering all these issues, the primary focus of this study is to identify the determinants of income, saving, and investment patterns of UG & PG teachers with reference to Mangalore city. The income and expenditure pattern and sources of income have a bearing on the saving and investment pattern. In the same way, the disposal of savings by the teachers, which in turn, depends on occupation, level of income, and level of education, needs a detailed analysis along with the determinants of income, saving, and investments of teachers. Through this study, it helps to gain more practical knowledge in the field of wealth management service. The present study will help know the investment awareness among the UG and PG teachers and the challenges faced by the teacher while investing and saving.

Statement of the problem:

There are many ways to get involved in types of investments, but they vary widely in the degree of risk and return and are certainly not appropriate or necessary for all investors. As the study Savings and Investment pattern of UG & PG teaching faculty in Mangalore city are concerned, the selection of the best saving and investment tool is a complicated process. This paper traces the Teaching faculty's savings and investment habit and their awareness of different types of avenues of expectations

Objectives of the study:

1. To study the savings and investment pattern of UG and PG Teachers.
2. To identify the savings and investment options they use currently and analyze the factors they consider while investing.
3. To know investment awareness among the UG & PG teachers.
4. To find out the problems faced by the UG & PG teachers while investing and provide suggestions based on the result obtained from the study.

Research Methodology:

The study is undertaken in Mangalore to know the saving and Investment pattern of UG & PG teachers.

Primary Data: It is collected from Questionnaire given to various UG and PG teachers in Mangalore. The Questionnaire was prepared keeping in view of Savings and Investing pattern of teachers.

Secondary Data: For this study secondary data was collected from various Books in Library and Internet.

The data that is collected is further tabulated in percentage. From the analysis carried out the

findings of the study is drawn and necessary suggestions are given.

Sample size:

The data is collected from 100 respondents with the help of structured questionnaire.

Sample Design:

A sample of 100 respondents is taken based on convenience sampling. This study was featured by a good number of salaried teachers of two scales - Under Graduate scale and Post Graduate Scale who are capable of saving and investing their surplus in different modes of savings and investment.

Data Analysis and Interpretations

Table 8.1: Demographic Data of the Respondents are given in the following table:

		No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Age:	Below 30	40	40
	30 – 35	30	30
	36 – 40	16	16
	41 – 45	6	6
	Above 45	8	8
Gender:	Female	70	70
	Male	30	30
Education:	Undergraduate	3	3
	Post graduation	70	70
	Above Post Graduation	27	27
Marital Status:	Married	64	64
	Unmarried	33	33
	Divorced	3	3
Income:	Below 250000	31	31
	25001 – 50,000	58	58
	50,000 – 75,000	6	6
	75,001 –1,00,000	1	1
	Above 1,00,000	4	4

Analysis & Interpretation:

The above table interprets the demographic data of the respondents. This type of classification helps in identifying the different preferences made by the respondents based on the Age, Gender, Education qualification, Marital status, Income. It is clear from the above table that most of the respondents are below the age of 30 years and few of the respondents belong to the age group 41-45 years. Majority of the respondents are female faculties. 70% of the respondents were post

graduates and 27% of the respondents were above post graduates. Most of the faculty respondents are married (64%). 33% of the respondents were unmarried and 3% of the respondents were divorced. It is clear from the above table that 58% of the respondents earn an income ranging from ₹25,000 - ₹50,000, 1% respondent earn an income between ₹75,001 - ₹100,000, and Majority of the faculty respondents earn an income ranging from ₹25000 - ₹50,000.

Table 8.2: Showing the Frequency of the Respondents with regards to Savings and Investment.

Frequency	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Daily	1	0.97
Weekly	2	1.95
Monthly	72	70.04
Quarterly	8	7.78
Half yearly	8	7.78
Annually	11	10.70
Occasionally	8	7.78
Total		

Source: Survey Data

N=100

MRR= 1.1

Note: 1. Percentage is not equal to 100 because of multiple Reponses.⁽³⁾

2. Multiple Response Rate (MRR) is equal to total number of responses divided by the number of respondents.⁽³⁾

Analysis & Interpretation:

From the above Information it has been analysed that 1 respondent saves and invests on a

daily basis, 2 respondents save and invest on a weekly basis, 72 respondents save and invest on a monthly basis, 8 respondents save and invest on a quarterly basis, 8 respondents save and invest half yearly, 11 respondents save and invest annually, and 8 respondents save and invest occasionally.

Here it has been interpreted that most of the faculty respondents save and invest on a monthly basis.

Table 8.3: Showing the Respondents Preference with regards to Savings and Investment Avenues/Strategies.

Avenues	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Bank deposits	73	70.08
Post Office Savings Scheme	47	45.12
Insurance policies	46	44.16
Government securities	4	3.84
Stocks/Mutual funds	28	26.88
Gold bonds/Gold jewellery	22	21.12
Real estate	3	2.88
Government schemes	1	0.96
Crypto currency	1	0.96
Total		
Source: Survey data		N= 100

MRR=2.25

Note: 1. Percentage is not equal to 100 because of multiple Reponses.⁽³⁾

2. Multiple Response Rate (MRR) is equal to total number of responses divided by the number of respondents.⁽³⁾

Analysis & Interpretation:

It is clear from the above data that 73 respondents prefer Bank deposits, 47 respondents prefer Post Office Savings Scheme, 46 respondents

prefer Insurance policies, 4 respondents prefer Government securities, 28 respondents prefer Stocks/Mutual funds, 22 respondents prefer Gold bonds/gold jewellery, 3 respondents prefer Real estate, 1 respondent prefer Government schemes, and 1 respondent prefer Crypto currency as their saving and investment platforms. Majority of the faculty respondents prefer investing in Bank deposits.

Table8.4: Showing the Duration of the Respondents Saving and Investment.

Duration	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Long term (more than 10 years)	40	38.4
Medium (more than 5 years)	43	41.28
Short term (more than 1 year)	36	34.56
Very short term (less than 1 year)	6	5.76
Total		
Source: Survey Data		N = 100

MRR= 1.15

Note: 1. Percentage is not equal to 100 because of multiple Reponses.⁽³⁾

2. Multiple Response Rate (MRR) is equal to total number of responses divided by the number of respondents.⁽³⁾

Analysis & Interpretation:

It is clear from the above data that 40 respondents prefer holding their savings and

investments for a long term (more than 10 years), 43 respondents prefer medium term investments (more than 5 years), 36 respondents prefer short term investments (more than 1 year), and 6 respondents prefer very short term investments (less than 1 year).Here it has been interpreted that most of the faculty respondents invest on a medium term basis i.e. on a scale of 5-10 years.

Table 8.5: Showing Factors considered by the respondents before making an Investment.

Factors	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Safety of principal	34	34
Low risk	29	29
High returns	23	23

Maturity period	9	9
Tax benefits	5	5
Total	100	100
Source: Survey data		N= 100

Analysis & Interpretation:

It is clear from the above data that the sample size is 100 respondents out of which 34% of the respondents mainly seek safety of the principal amount, 29% of the respondents prefer low risk, 23% of the respondents seek high returns on their

investment, 9% of the respondents consider maturity period, and 5% of the respondents focus on tax benefits from their investments. Based on the above information it has been interpreted that most of the faculty respondents consider safety of principal as a factor before making an investment.

Table 8.6: Showing Source of Saving and Investment advice the respondents seek before making an Investment.

Source	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Family members	38	38
Financial advisors	14	14
Friends/colleagues	20	20
Self-decision	28	28
Total	100	100

Source: Survey data

N=100

Analysis & Interpretation:

From the above data it is clear that out of 100 respondents 38% of the respondents seek saving & investment advice from family members, 14% of the respondents seek advice from financial advisors,

20% of the respondents seek advice from friends/colleagues, and 28% of the respondents take saving & investment decisions on their own (self-decision). Majority of the faculty respondents seek savings & investment advice from family members.

Table 8.7: Showing source of Information for the respondents Savings and Investment

Source of Investment	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
TV & Radio	9	9
Friends & Relatives	67	67
Newspaper & Magazine	17	17
Internet	2	2
Mobile phone	1	1
Bank website	1	1
Acquired intuition	1	1
Blogs	1	1
YouTube	1	1
Total	100	100

Source: Survey data

N=100

Analysis & Interpretation:

It is clear from the above data that out of 100 respondents 9 respondents prefer TV & Radio as the source of information for their saving and investment, 67 respondents prefer friends & relatives, 17 respondents prefer newspaper & magazine, 2 respondents prefer Internet, 1 respondent prefer mobile phone, 1 respondent prefer

bank website, 1 respondent prefer acquired intuition, 1 respondent prefer blogs, and 1 respondent prefer YouTube as their sources of information for saving and investment. Here it has been interpreted that majority of the faculty respondents prefer friends & relatives as their source of information for savings and investment.

Table 8.8: The data is collected from 100 respondents with the help of structured questionnaire based on convenience sampling.

Problems	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Lack of knowledge	22	22
Trust issues	13	13
Inadequate disclosure	4	4
Bad experience	3	3
TOTAL	42	42

Source: Survey data

N=100

Analysis & Interpretation:

From the above table it has been analysed that 22 respondents feel that lack of knowledge about savings and investment is the problem they face, 13 respondents have trust issues with the companies that provide savings and investment services, 4 respondents face a problem of inadequate disclosure, and 3 respondents have had bad experiences with saving and investing. **Majority of the faculty respondents lack knowledge with regards to savings and investments.**

Findings:

- It can be observed that 70% of the respondents are female faculties.
- It can be analyzed that majority of the faculty respondents are post graduates.
- The study found that full time faculties are more in number as compared to the part time faculties.
- The study concluded that 96% of the faculty respondents have the habit of saving and investing their money.
- The study clearly indicates that 73% of the respondents prefer investing in Bank deposits.
- The study interpreted that most of the respondents invest on a medium term basis i.e., on a scale of 5 – 10 years.
- It can be observed that 38% of the respondents seek savings and investment advice from family members.
- Majority of the respondents agreed that they integrally know the details of their investment strategies such as taxation, liquidation, return and risk associated.
- 58% of the respondents have not faced any problem before/after making savings and investment.
- Majority of the respondents lack knowledge with regards to savings and investment.

Limitations of the study:

- The scope of the study was limited to Mangalore city.
- Only a small sample size of the consumer was studied, which may not be enough to give the correct picture.
- Respondents' bias. The accuracy of the primary data depends on the information given by the respondents through the questionnaire.
- The preference for schemes of savings and investment keeps changing from time to time, therefore the study is valid up to a specific period only.

Suggestions:

- Teachers should go for expert advice before investing and saving
- Respondents should remove the fear of insecurity from the mind.
- Teachers can also invest in long term securities.

- They need to be aware of the market situation and invest accordingly.
- Respondents should update their knowledge about new investment avenues.

Conclusion:

Teachers are an important force in our society, as they are guarantors of the education of future generations, especially in developing countries like India. The study is mainly conducted to identify the saving and investment pattern adopted by the UG & PG teachers of Mangalore city. The study analyses the various factors which influence the investment decisions of the teachers. It is found that bank deposit is the favourite avenue of almost all respondents. From this study it is clear that saving and investment is important. Most of the teachers make investment, from the influence by self, by family and relatives. But majority of the teachers were afraid to take risk.

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